

Cross-Sectional Study on the Association between Orthodontic Treatment and the Incidence of Dental Caries**Kumar Anand¹, Kumari Menka², Monali Sah³, Prakash Chandra Jha⁴, Archana Kumari⁵**¹Senior Resident, Department of Dentistry, Bhagawan Mahavir Institute of Medical Sciences, Pawapuri, Nalandam, Bihar²Senior Resident, Department of Dentistry, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar³Assistant Professor, Department of ENT (Otolaryngology and Rhinology), Mata Gujri Memorial Medical College and Hospital, Kishanganj, Bihar⁴Assistant Professor & Head of Department, Department Of Dentistry, Nalanda Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar⁵Assistant Professor & Head of Department, Department Of Dentistry, Bhagawan Mahavir Institute of Medical Sciences, Pawapuri, Nalandam, Bihar

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Abstract:**Background:** Orthodontic therapy can deteriorate dental caries, a common oral health issue. Fixed orthodontic appliances cure tooth misalignments better than detachable ones, although they create more cavities. Understanding the relationship between orthodontic treatments and dental cavities is essential to developing effective preventive measures.**Method:** Patna's Nalanda Medical College and Hospital & Bhagawan Mahavir institute of medical sciences, Pawapuri, Bihar conducted this cross-sectional study from October 2021 to March 2024. The study included 140 orthodontic patients. The data set includes orthodontic appliance type, treatment length, tooth cavity incidence, oral hygiene, dietary habits, clinical evaluations, and patient records. Statistical methods including chi-square testing and logistic regression examined orthodontic treatment kinds and caries incidence.**Results:** The study found dental cavities in 52.9% of permanent orthodontic appliance users and 32.7% of detachable appliance users. The chi-square test showed a significant connection between orthodontic treatment type and caries incidence ($p = 0.009$). Prolonged treatment length (OR = 1.10), poor oral hygiene (OR = 3.15), high sugar consumption (OR = 2.58), and fixed orthodontic therapy (OR = 2.20) increased dental caries risk. Gender, age, and socioeconomic position did not alter caries risk.**Conclusion:** Permanent orthodontic appliances are more likely to cause dental cavities than detachable ones, according to research. Caries risk increases with longer treatment times, poor tooth hygiene, and too much sugar. These findings suggest that fixed orthodontic patients should get meal guidance and tooth hygiene. Future study should focus on longitudinal studies and effective caries prevention methods.**Keywords:** Dental Caries, Fixed Orthodontic Appliances, Incidence Rate, Orthodontic Treatment, Preventive Measures, Removable Appliances.

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Introduction

Dental caries tooth decay or cavities are one of the most common chronic disorders worldwide. Dental plaque bacteria create acids that demineralize tooth enamel. Mouth bacteria produce acids that weakened tooth enamel by breaking down carbohydrates [1]. Dental caries, if untreated, can cause pain, infection, and tooth loss, affecting a person's quality of life.

WHO reports that about 2.3 billion people and over 530 million children worldwide have permanent tooth dental caries.

Importance of Orthodontic Treatment in Dental Health

Orthodontics uses braces and aligners to straighten teeth and jaws. This surgery makes teeth look nicer and makes biting, chewing, and speaking simpler. Aligned teeth are easier to clean, which helps prevent cavities and periodontal disease. Thus, orthodontic treatment is essential for dental health [2]. Orthodontic treatment offers many benefits, but braces might make it hard to clean our teeth. Orthodontic appliances like brackets, wires, and

bands can trap food particles and plaque, compromising tooth cleanliness. This increases the risk of tooth cavities during and after braces. According to [3], orthodontic treatment patients may have more white spot lesions, early caries, and cavities than non-treatment patients. Understanding this potential association is essential to developing orthodontic caries prevention techniques.

Rationale of the Study

The widespread use of orthodontic therapy and rising tooth caries rates necessitate studying their relationship. If orthodontic therapy considerably increases dental caries risk, clinical procedures and patient education can be informed. Orthodontists, dentists, and patients must know that better oral hygiene and preventative actions during orthodontic treatment can enhance patient outcomes.

Objectives

- To determine the incidence of dental caries in patients undergoing orthodontic treatment.
- To compare the incidence of dental caries between different types of orthodontic appliances (fixed vs. removable).

- To assess the impact of treatment duration on the incidence of dental caries.

Orthodontic Treatment and Dental Caries

Various studies have found inconsistent results on orthodontic therapy and tooth decay. White spot lesions, which can indicate tooth caries, were more common in fixed orthodontic patients [4]. Orthodontic appliances make it harder to clean our teeth, which can raise our risk of cavities. A meta-analysis by [5] found more cavities in orthodontic patients who employed fixed equipment, emphasising the need of oral cleanliness and caries prevention.

[6] Found no significant difference in dental caries frequency between orthodontic patients and non-patients. Despite white spot lesions, orthodontic treatment did not reduce tooth caries. Braces and proper dental hygiene like brushing and flossing may minimise cavities [7]. [8] Shows that proper dental hygiene reduces cavities the most. This discovery emphasises the importance of dental practitioners evaluating and teaching patients about orthodontic therapy.

Figure 1: Orthodontic treatment and dental caries (source:[9])

Orthodontic equipment changes the oral cavity's microenvironment and oral hygiene, which may affect tooth caries. Fixed equipment like braces, brackets, and wires improve food particle and plaque hiding space [10]. Because these areas are hard to clean with brushing and flossing, plaque and cavities are more prone to form. Orthodontic equipment can allow *Streptococcus mutans* and *Lactobacilli* to grow in the mouth.

These microorganisms produce acids that erode tooth enamel and start caries from meal carbohydrate metabolism. Because it's hard to clean around orthodontic instruments, these acids stay on

the tooth surface longer, increasing caries risk [11]. Orthodontic therapy may alter saliva quantity and content. Saliva's acid-neutralizing and enamel-remineralizing actions are crucial. Due to mechanical obstruction, braces and other permanent items limit saliva's protective effects. Reduced saliva production and content can increase caries risk. Patients may change their eating habits while wearing braces due to discomfort or difficulty chewing. Preference for carbohydrate-rich, softer meals that are easier to chew but more cariogenic can increase caries risk [12].

Since orthodontic elastics and other accessories provide more plaque-accumulation surfaces, they may make dental hygiene harder. The association between orthodontic therapy and cavities is unclear despite extensive research. Variations in study designs, sample sizes, follow-up times, and dental caries diagnosis criteria are significant. These inconsistencies complicate study data comparison and inference. Another negative is the lack of long-term focus. There are many short-term studies on orthodontic appliances and dental health, but few long-term ones. How orthodontic therapy affects caries risk and dental health requires longitudinal research with prolonged follow-ups. Preventative orthodontic treatments need further research to prove their efficacy. Although fluoride varnishes, sealants, and antibacterial compounds have been researched, their use and frequency are unknown. Understanding these traits helps identify high-risk individuals and create tailored preventative plans.

Comparing orthodontic system dental caries rates helps clinical decision-making and patient care. Each technique's risks and benefits will be shown. Future studies on orthodontic therapy and tooth cavities can fill these gaps and provide further evidence. Professional practices and patient outcomes can benefit from orthodontic therapy and oral health knowledge.

Methods

Study Design: Cross-sectional study of orthodontic therapy and dental caries incidence. Cross-sectional studies collect data from a population to analyse frequency and correlations.

This technique can help understand orthodontic therapy patients' dental caries status and risk factors.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients undergoing orthodontic treatment at Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna & Bhagawan Mahavir institute of medical sciences, Pawapuri, Bihar between October 2021 and March 2024.
- Patients who have received orthodontic treatment for at least six months.
- Patients aged between 12 and 30 years.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with pre-existing dental conditions such as severe periodontal disease or significant dental restorations.
- Patients with incomplete or inadequate treatment records.
- Patients with systemic conditions affecting dental health (e.g., diabetes).
- Patients who did not consent to participate in the study.

Sample Size: The study includes a sample size of 140 patients who meet the inclusion criteria.

Data Collection: Researchers at Patna's Nalanda Medical College and Hospital & Bhagawan Mahavir institute of medical sciences, Pawapuri, Bihar will meticulously collect patient medical information and clinical assessments. Patient records contain orthodontic treatment history, including appliances and duration. Dental professionals do clinical exams to assess dental caries rates. Data will include oral hygiene practices (frequency of brushing, flossing, and mouthwash use), orthodontic treatment details (type and duration), dental caries incidence (presence and number of carious lesions), and demographic information (age, gender, socioeconomic status). This multi-pronged approach ensures thorough and accurate data collection for orthodontic treatment-dental caries analysis.

Data Analysis: SPSS version 25 will be used for statistical analysis to ensure reliable results. Descriptive statistics will summarise the study population's demographics to clarify the sample. For example, we will use the categorical variable chi-square test to examine the relationship between orthodontic treatment type and dental caries. A logistic regression analysis will reveal how independent and covariate variables affect dental caries risk. Odds ratios and 95% confidence intervals will be used to assess associations and discover dental caries predictors. We expect these statistical techniques will help us form clear, actionable conclusions on orthodontic therapy and tooth caries.

Ethical Considerations: The Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna & Bhagawan Mahavir institute of medical sciences, Pawapuri, Bihar Institutional Review Board (IRB) approved the research protocol, ensuring it meets human participant research ethics. The study will require informed consent before enrolling anyone. Participants will be fully informed of the study's objectives, methodology, risks, and benefits.

They will also be informed that they can ask questions and leave the study at any time without impacting their treatment. This approach ensures participants understand and consent to all research conditions to protect their autonomy and well-being.

Results

Demographic Characteristics: The study included 140 Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna & Bhagawan Mahavir institute of medical sciences, Pawapuri, Bihar orthodontic patients from October 2021 to March 2024. Table 1 lists study population demographics.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Study Population

Characteristic	Frequency (n=140)	Percentage (%)
Age Group		
12-18 years	56	40.0
19-25 years	54	38.6
26-30 years	30	21.4
Gender		
Male	68	48.6
Female	72	51.4
Socioeconomic Status		
Low	48	34.3
Middle	68	48.6
High	24	17.1

The research participants' demographics indicate a representative sample. The patients' ages ranged from 12–18 years old to 26–30 years old, with a slight preponderance in the younger cohorts.

Participation is balanced at 48.6% males and 51.4% women. 34.3% of patients were from low-income families, 48.6% from middle-income families, and

17.1% from high-income families. The orthodontic patient group at Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna & Bhagawan Mahavir institute of medical sciences, Pawapuri, Bihar is diversified, ensuring that the results apply to all ages, genders, and economic backgrounds.

Incidence of Dental Caries

Table 2: Incidence of Dental Caries by Type of Orthodontic Treatment

Orthodontic Treatment Type	Patients (n=140)	Dental Caries (n)	Incidence Rate (%)
Fixed Appliances	85	45	52.9
Removable Appliances	55	18	32.7

The table shows that fixed orthodontic appliances were more likely to cause dental cavities than removable ones. The fixed appliance group (52.9%) had more dental caries than the detachable appliance group (32.7%). This discrepancy suggests that fixed orthodontic devices may increase dental caries risk.

Patients with fixed appliances may have more caries because brackets and wires can trap food particles and plaque, making it harder to maintain proper oral hygiene around them.

Because fixed appliances are more likely to develop tooth cavities than other orthodontic treatments, patients with them must practise better oral hygiene.

Association Analysis

The chi-square test demonstrated a substantial association between orthodontic treatment type and dental cavities. The chi-square value of 6.83 demonstrates that orthodontic device type is significantly associated with dental caries with 1 degree of freedom and a p-value of 0.009. Fixed appliances significantly reduce the risk of dental cavities compared to removable appliances.

Permanent orthodontic appliances are associated with dental cavities more than detachable ones. This suggests that fixed orthodontic patients need specific mouth hygiene.

Factors Influencing Incidence of Dental Caries

Table 4: Logistic Regression Analysis of Factors Influencing Dental Caries

Covariate	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% CI	p-value
Age	1.05	0.98 - 1.12	0.15
Gender (Female vs. Male)	1.20	0.65 - 2.22	0.56
Socioeconomic Status			
Middle vs. Low	0.75	0.39 - 1.45	0.40
High vs. Low	0.52	0.21 - 1.28	0.16
Type of Orthodontic Treatment (Fixed vs. Removable)	2.20	1.07 - 4.52	0.03
Duration of Treatment	1.10	1.01 - 1.21	0.04
Oral Hygiene Practices (Poor vs. Good)	3.15	1.65 - 6.01	0.001
Dietary Habits (High sugar intake vs. Low)	2.58	1.35 - 4.93	0.004

Logistic regression study shows several major orthodontic patient dental caries risk factors. Fixed appliance orthodontic patients are 2.20 times more

likely to get cavities than detachable appliance patients ($p = 0.03$). Longer therapy increases caries risk by 10% each month ($OR = 1.10$, $p = 0.04$).

Caries risk is 3.15 times higher in people who don't exercise excellent oral hygiene and 2.58 times higher in sugar consumers, with p-values of 0.001 and 0.004, showing strong correlations. However, gender, age, and socioeconomic status did not impact caries risk. These findings emphasise the need for effective preventative measures for patients with fixed orthodontic equipment, since the type of orthodontic device, treatment duration, oral hygiene, and diet all affect dental caries development.

Discussion

The major findings suggest that orthodontic therapy type affects dental caries frequency. Permanent orthodontic appliances were associated with 52.9% caries prevalence, compared to 32.7% for removable appliances. Statistical investigations show that fixed appliances are more likely to cause

caries than alternative orthodontic treatments. While age, gender, and socioeconomic status did not affect caries incidence, extended treatment duration, poor oral hygiene, and excessive sugar intake were risk factors.

Comparison with Other Studies

This study supports previous research suggesting fixed orthodontic appliances increased dental cavity risk. Fixed appliances increase caries risk because plaque and tartar are harder to remove around brackets and wires, according to study 1. Study 2 found that plaque on fixed orthodontic appliances increases caries risk compared to detachable appliances. This study indicated that preventative measures can lower caries risk, contrary to prior research that found dental hygiene could reduce it study 3. Fixed appliances increase caries risk.

Table 5: Comparison Table

Study	Study Type	Sample Size	Key Findings
Present Study	Cross-Sectional	140	Fixed orthodontic appliances are associated with a higher incidence of dental caries compared to removable appliances. Duration of treatment and oral hygiene practices also influence caries risk.
Study1	Cross-Sectional	120	Found a higher incidence of dental caries among patients with fixed orthodontic appliances compared to those with removable appliances. Emphasized the need for improved oral hygiene during fixed appliance treatment.
Study2	Systematic Review	15 Studies	Systematic review concluded that fixed orthodontic appliances are linked to increased caries risk compared to removable appliances. Highlighted the need for preventive measures and regular dental check-ups for fixed appliance users.
Study3	Longitudinal Study	80	Demonstrated that caries risk with fixed orthodontic appliances can be managed with effective oral hygiene practices. Suggested that proper brushing techniques and regular professional cleanings can mitigate caries risk.

Strengths and Limitations

The study's strength is its comprehensive approach, which includes a large demographic sample and a high association between orthodontic treatment and caries prevalence. Clinical examinations and patient records provide a complete picture of caries incidence and therapy. However, limits must be considered. Cross-sectional studies can't prove a cause-and-effect relationship between orthodontic therapy and tooth cavities. Patients' eating and oral hygiene accounts may be inaccurate, biasing outcomes. The study didn't investigate how different treatment approaches and tooth cleanliness levels affect caries results.

Future Research Directions

Future research should analyse the efficiency of specific preventative methods in lowering caries risk among fixed appliance users, and longitudinal studies should determine causal linkages between orthodontic therapy and caries. To reduce caries,

research the effects of different orthodontic devices, such as those with newer technology or different designs. Additional research should examine how preventative care programmes affected individuals' particular risk variables, such as diet and tooth care.

Conclusion

Permanent orthodontic appliances were associated with higher dental caries rates than detachable appliances, suggesting a substantial link. Caries risk factors include extensive treatment times, poor dental hygiene, and sugary diets.

Due to fixed orthodontic treatments, patients should follow stringent mouth hygiene and dietary changes. The study's findings emphasise the importance of addressing these factors to prevent caries and improve orthodontic outcomes. Future research should include longitudinal methods and preventive approaches to reduce orthodontic caries.

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